

Long-Term Domestic Care as Health Care of Chronic and Disabled Patients

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Abstract

The completion of health services by the nurse in charge of the long term domestic care is the health care of the bed-ridden and disabled patient in his home environment. This health care is performed by the nurse free of charge while maintaining continuity and unflinching regularity in the nursing of the patient. Discussion on the tasks given to the nurse providing the health care at patient's home. Presentation of good points and possibilities that have been introduced to the health policy by long term domestic care of the chronic and disabled patient. The research material was obtained from the pilot studies performed on 40 persons provided with long term domestic care by graduate nurses. The studies were carried out on 20 patients who lived in the Lublin province and from 20 patients who lived in the Silesian province during the period between September 2005 and January 2006. Long-term domestic care is the cheapest form of the health care available for a chronic and disabled patient. Patient provided with this form of care has assured its continuity for a period from 3 to 6 months. When there is no improvement in the state of the patient's health there is the possibility to continue this form of care after approval by the National Fund of Health Service. Each person provided with long term domestic care has assured sense of security which improves their comfort of life during the long-standing disease.

Keywords: health services, long term domestic care

Introduction

The realization of health services performed by the nurse of the long term domestic care is the health care of the bed-ridden and disabled patients at their home environment. The patients that are looked after by the nurse at their home environment should feel higher comfort of life and thus the improved quality of life [5]. The health care is performed by the nurse free of charge with maintenance of the continuity and regularity in caring the sick persons. The sick persons with chronic illness complain of subjective and objective signs which manifest as the physical, psychic and developmental disorders of functions of the organism. Chronic diseases may have course with periods of aggravation and remission and hence the state of the man's health may undergo continuous changes. The health care provided at patient home by long-term home nurse has the following aims: to recognize the health conditions and health needs, to identify the nursing problems, to take nursing care. It

should also realize the physician's instructions in the process of diagnostics, treatment and rehabilitation, provide independently in a specific range the prophylactic, therapeutic and rehabilitation services and also the health education [8]. Individual elements of the health care are subjected to an appraisal by means of the appropriately chosen criteria. The criteria that are most frequently used for the evaluation of the quality of the nursing care are following: sense of security of the patient provided with the long term domestic care, individualization, the care adapted individually for the needs of chronic and disabled, patient, effectiveness, continuity, ethicality, professionalism, availability, orienting toward prophylaxis [6]. The chronic and disabled patients are provided with long-term domestic care that is free of charge during the period ranging from 3 to 6 months. The total cost of the performed health service is paid by the National Health Fund. The state of health of the chronic and disabled patients in many instances requires the health services to be continued.

Aims of Work

1. Elaboration of the tasks that should be done by the nurse providing the health care at patient's home.
2. Depicting the merits and possibilities that the long-term domestic care of the chronic patient is bringing to the health policy.

Material and Method

The research material was collected on the basis of the pilot studies of 40 persons provided with long-term domestic care by the graduate nurses. The studies were carried out on 20 patients from the Lublin province and 20 patients from the Silesian province. They were performed during the period ranging between September 2005 and January 2006. All studied persons were chronic and disabled, were in a geriatric age and were dependent on other persons. The choice of two different provinces was intentional because it gave to possibility to disclose differences that may exist between them in taking long term domestic care. In the Silesian province the domestic care seems to function in the environment that is much more thriving and thus the persons needing such kind of protection have better access to this type of the health care than the patients in the Lublin province.

Results

The health care provided at patient's home is a specialist form of the nursing care that is directed toward persons that require this form of protection because of their state of health. The chronic and disable patients are provided with long term domestic care without charge for a period lasting 3 to 6 months and the total expenses of the performed health services are covered by the Natinal Health Fund. The disability of the patient disturbs his functioning in the personality, family, social and occupational spheres [11]. In order to im-

prove the quality of life of the chronic and disabled patient one can use orthopaedic supply and auxiliary materials [9]. Table 1 shows that the disabled patients have been informed about the possibility of use of orthopaedic supply first of all by the nurses providing them with long term domestic care. Such an answer was given by 60% of patients living in the Silesian province and 50% of patients in the Lublin province (Table 1). The patients were then asked who has taught them to use the orthopaedic supply. The nurse providing the long term domestic care did it in about 83% in the Silesian province and only in 50% in the Lublin province. It may be also seen that in the Silesian province the physician and the physiotherapist had very small (about 6%) influence on teaching the patient to use the specific orthopaedic supply. These values may be related with better organization of the long term domestic care in the Silesian province where the nurse is more independent in her work with the chronic patient (Table 2). In the situation when in the chronic and disabled patients there is the problem of the urinary and fecal incontinence, we observed the appearance of other ailments which disturb the comfort of their life [5, 7]. We have asked the studied group of patients whether they had complaints concerning the urinary and fecal incontinence (Table 3). There is significant difference between the rate of occurrence of ailments related with urinary and fecal incontinence in the Silesian (80%) and Lublin (60%) provinces. This may be connected with much worse state of health in patients provided with the long term domestic care in the Silesian province. The urinary and fecal incontinence also named the sphincter flaccidity is the most frequently encountered problem appearing in persons subjected to the long term domestic care. Most frequently the patients are helpless, feel lonely and expect extensive help from the nurse taking long term domestic care [4]. The systematic and consequently conducted nursing care permits to alleviate and smooth away the existing health problems [10]. In both studied groups all respondents (that is 100%) answered that the health care conducted by the nurse is needed (Table 4). A very important health service carried out by the nurse at home of the chronic and disabled patients consists in performing dress-

Table 1. Persons who informed patients about the possibility of use of orthopaedic supply.

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	N	%	N	%
Physician	5	25.00	9	36.00
Nurse	12	60.00	13	52.00
Physiotherapist	0	0.00	0	0.00
Neighbour	3	15.00	3	12.00
Total	20	100.00	25	100.00
χ^2	2.358			
P	<0.05			

Table 2. Persons who taught patients to use properly the orthopaedic supply.

	Silesian Province		Lublin province	
	N	%	N	%
Physician	1	5.88	4	18.18
Nurse	14	82.35	11	50.00
Physiotherapist	1	5.88	2	9.09
Neighbour	1	5.88	5	22.73
Total	17	100.00	22	100.00
χ^2	1.089			
P	>0.05			

ings aimed at treating the decubitus ulcers, wounds showing delayed healing and trophic ulcerations of shanks [1]. Two groups of the studied patients were asked whether they have indications that are related with their state of health for regular performance of dressings. 85% of patients living in the Silesian province answered that such indications appeared. The number of inhabitants of the Lublin province that gave the same answer amounted only to 65% (Table 5). Table 6 shows that there was no significant difference in the treatment of trophic ulcerations of shanks in patients of both studied provinces. The treatment of wounds showing delayed healing was more frequent in the Lublin province (about 53%) than in the Silesian province (39%). As concerns the treatment of decubitus ulcers it was performed

more frequently in the Silesian (in 39%) as compared with the Lublin province (20%) (Table 6). The development of the market of long term domestic care permits chronic and disabled patients that demand to realize their nurse services for the safe life in their home environment where everybody should feel the best. It should be stressed here that the steady development of long term domestic care considerably decreases the financial outlays in the medical care. In the situation when there are indications to perform such services as: regular performance of dressings, the nursing of the skin, antidecubitus prophylaxis, increasing of patient efficiency in his around the bed activities, keeping him in vertical posture and the selection of proper orthopaedic supply and of ancillary means, the education of the patient and his family, supporting patient in his positive health habits; all these activities should be carried out at patient's home by the nurse performing the long term domestic care. When the nursing process is conducted in such manner, it is possible to monitor the health state of patients and in this way to decrease the financial outlays for the medical care directed to the patients staying at their environment [3, 10]. The patient that is appropriately cared at home to much lesser extent needs visits of the family doctor, specialist and more rarely uses the emergency ambulance service. Table 7 shows the frequency of the family doctors visits in both studied groups of patients. The patients from both provinces responded in very

Table 3. Incidence of ailments connected with urinary and fecal incontinence.

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	N	%	N	%
Yes	16	80.00	12	60.00
No	4	20.00	8	40.00
Total	20	100.00	20	100.00
χ^2	3.529			
P	<0.05			

Table 4. Is the health care conducted by the nurse needed in the discussed situation.

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	N	%	N	%
Yes	20	100.00	20	100.00
No	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	20	100.00	20	100.00
χ^2	-			
P	-			

Table 5. Indications for regular performance of dressings.

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	N	%	N	%
Yes	17	85.00	13	65.00
No	3	15.00	7	35.00
Total	20	100.00	20	100.00
χ^2	2.478			
P	<0.05			

Table 6. Causes for regular performance of dressings in patients provided with long-term domestic care.

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	N	%	N	%
Wounds showing delayed healing	7	38.89	8	53.33
Trophic ulcerations of shanks	4	22.22	4	26.67
Decubitus ulcers	7	38.89	3	20.00
Total	18	100.00	15	100.00
χ^2	0.789			
P	>0.05			

Table 7. Is family doctor asked frequently to make round since the patients were provided with long-term domestic care.

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	N	%	N	%
Yes	3	15.00	1	5.00
No	17	85.00	19	95.00
Total	20	100.00	20	100.00
χ^2	1.005			
P	>0.05			

Table 8. Number of visits at patients homes performed by family doctor since they were provided with long-term domestic care.

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	N	%	N	%
About 10	2	10.00	0	0.00
About 5	3	15.00	1	5.00
Less than 5	15	75.00	19	95.00
Total	20	100.00	20	100.00
χ^2	0.098			
P	>0.05			

Table 9. Number of reports of emergency ambulance service since the patients were provided with long term domestic care.

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	N	%	N	%
About 3	0	0.00	1	5.00
Less than 3	6	30.00	4	20.00
Not any	14	70.00	15	75.00
Total	20	100.00	20	100.00
χ^2	0.745			
P	>0.05			

similar way. 85% of patients from the Silesian province and 95% from the Lublin province told that since they were provided with long term domestic care, the family doctors were asked to make round more rarely (Table 7). Table 8 shows in detail the incidence of the family doctors visits in patients provided with long term domestic care. One can note again the lack of basic differences in responses of patients of two compared provinces. These responses may suggest that the patients provided with long term domestic care consider the nurse services performed at home as the health service (Table 8). The patients were also asked about the number of reports of the emergency ambulance service (Table 9). Both compared groups responded in a similar way. 70% of patients in the Silesian province and 75% of patients in the Lublin province did not reported any ambulance and below three reports were made 30% of patients from the Silesian province and 25% of patients from the Lublin province.

Discussion

The potential need for long-term domestic care can be analysed in three dimensions: somatic diseases (medical diagnosis, nurse diagnosis), disability: physical and psychic, social or economic [3]. Domestic care develops very

rapidly because the procedures that were previously performed at hospitals are nowadays transferred to patients homes. This is in agreement with more general trend to depart from the hospital services [3]. The severe and long lasting disease, disability and old age make the human life very difficult. The people suffer various ailments and limitations, experience fears, tensions, breakdowns, the sense of threat, and at the same time the helplessness; they suffer and fall into depression [4, 7].

Conclusions

1. Long-term domestic care is a specialist form and at the same time the cheapest form of health services performed at patients homes.
2. Patient provided with this form of care during the period from 3 to 6 months has ensured regular nursing care.
3. When no amelioration in the state of patient is observed there is possibility, after receiving approval from the National Health Fund, to continue this form of the health care.
4. There were no fundamental differences in the performed health care between patients provided with long-term domestic care that were living in both provinces.
5. Each person included into long-term domestic care has ensured sense of security which ameliorates their comfort of life during chronic illness.

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